

Graphical Abstract

Standardized Multi-Layer Tissue Maps for Enhanced Artificial Intelligence Integration and Search in Large-Scale Whole Slide Image Archives

Gernot Fiala[‡], Markus Plass[‡], Robert Harb, Peter Regitnig, Kristijan Skok, Wael Al Zoughbi, Carmen Zerner, Paul Torke, Michaela Kargl, Heimo Müller, Tomas Brazdil, Matej Gallo, Jaroslav Kubín, Roman Stoklasa, Rudolf Nenužil, Norman Zerbe, Andreas Holzinger, Petr Holub

Tissue map visualization framework

Tissue map integration into WSI archives

[‡] These authors contributed equally to this work.

Highlights

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- Metadata model enabling effective search in large-scale collections of WSIs.
- Metadata model contributes to the community standards of BBMRI-ERIC.
- The model includes coarse-grained multi-layer tissue maps providing metadata.
- Proof-of-concept implementation for generating multi-layer tissue maps.

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Standardized Multi-Layer Tissue Maps for Enhanced Artificial Intelligence Integration and Search in Large-Scale Whole Slide Image Archives

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Abstract

A Whole Slide Image (WSI) is a high-resolution digital image created by scanning an entire glass slide containing a biological specimen, such as tissue sections or cell samples, at multiple magnifications. These images can be viewed, analyzed, shared digitally, and are used today for Artificial Intelligence (AI) algorithm development. WSIs are used in a variety of fields, including pathology for diagnosing diseases and oncology for cancer research.

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They are also utilized in neurology, veterinary medicine, hematology, microbiology, dermatology, pharmacology, toxicology, immunology, and forensic science.

When assembling cohorts for the training or validation of an AI algorithm, it is essential to know what is present on such a WSI. However, there is currently no standard for this metadata, so such selection has mainly been done through manual inspection, which is not suitable for large collections with several million objects.

We propose a general framework to generate a 2D index map for WSI and a profiling mechanism for specific application domains. We demonstrate this approach in the field of clinical pathology, using common syntax and semantics to achieve interoperability between different catalogs.

Our approach augments each WSI collection with a detailed tissue map that provides fine-grained information about the WSI content. The tissue map is organized into three layers: source, tissue type, and pathological alterations, with each layer assigning segments of the WSI to specific classes.

We illustrate the advantages and applicability of the proposed standard through specific examples in WSI catalogs, Machine Learning (ML), and graph-based WSI representations.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, Digital pathology, Machine learning, Metadata, Whole slide image archive, Whole slide image catalog

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1. Introduction

A Whole Slide Image (WSI) is a high-resolution digital image that is created by scanning an entire glass slide containing tissue sections or cell samples of a biological specimen at high magnification. This results in gigapixel images with resolutions of up to $150,000 \times 150,000$ pixels and pixel sizes of down to $0.125 \mu\text{m}$. They are represented as image pyramids with different magnification levels, shown in Figure 1(a). Details of an example WSI from The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA)^{1,2} dataset at different magnifications are shown in Figure 1(b).

Such images are viewable, analyzable, and shareable through digital means and most importantly, they are utilized in developing AI algorithms today. There are various applications of WSIs in fields such as pathology where they

Figure 1: WSI example from TCGA breast dataset. (a) WSI pyramid with down-sampled pyramid levels. (b) Details at different magnification levels.

become crucial for diagnosing diseases and oncology where they play a big role in cancer research³⁻⁵.

Moreover, they study brain disorders in neurology⁶ and diagnose diseases in animals like those in veterinary medicine⁷. In addition to that, these images can be used for other purposes besides the ones mentioned above including hematology to look at blood samples⁸; microbiology to identify microorganisms; dermatology which diagnoses skin conditions⁹; pharmacology¹⁰ and toxicology involved with drug development/ toxicity testing on pharmaceuticals¹¹. Immunologists also use them to investigate immune responses within tissues while forensic scientists examine biological evidence.

It is important to know the specimen composition of a WSI when forming its cohorts to train or validate an AI algorithm. Nevertheless, there is no standard for such metadata at the moment. Hence, such selections are mostly guided by manual assessments, which work quite well if there are only several hundred or thousand WSIs but not in the case of, e.g., pathology with millions of objects. It becomes apparent that metadata standardization and search indices are required when working with large collections such as those found in pathology where hundreds of thousands to several million items may be present. For instance, without approved metadata, selecting suitable WSIs for training or validating any AI system would be difficult, thus hampering large-scale experiments and improvements in AI applications. By creating a comprehensive metadata standard and establishing a fast search index, the process of choosing appropriate WSIs would become more efficient,

Figure 2: Overview of a pathological workflow.

allowing for more impact research and development in medical and scientific fields.

Moreover, integration of standardized metadata in WSIs can significantly enhance the reproducibility of studies. Researchers and clinicians can consistently identify and utilize relevant slides and also accelerate the pace of discoveries. Discoveries in disease diagnosis, treatment and prevention would benefit. It would also accelerate and improve the development of AI algorithms by faster selection of WSIs and their better balancing for cohorts. The future of pathology and related disciplines lies in harnessing the full potential of digital technologies. Thus, the establishment of comprehensive metadata standards is an urgent and essential priority.

The process of a typical pathological case is shown in Figure 2. A sample extraction takes place from the patient either by biopsy, surgery etc. The tissue specimen is prepared by macroscopy and blocks are created out of tissue parts. Thin tissue slices are cut from the blocks and placed on glass slides. Afterwards, the glass slides are stained or treated with immunohistochemistry (IHC). Then, the slides are digitized by scanners and provided for diagnostics. Finally, the diagnosis, scanned slides (WSIs), blocks and glass slides are archived. Pathologists and researchers can request slides from the archive for research purposes. A case can contain multiple steps of staining or IHC preparation of the slides. Each of these slides are scanned, which result in several WSIs per case.

More and more pathology institutions are currently switching to digitize glass slides. This has the advantage of easier access to WSIs between the

Organ	# Cases	Slides	Av. Slides/Case	Lymph	IHC
Colon	7830	31920	4.07	876	2225
Prostate	1989	48398	7.27	46	782
Mamma	1461	14464	10.99	86	3385
Lung	1058	10090	9.54	396	1808
Liver	585	6102	10.43	17	1612
Kidney	583	9396	16.12	42	2184
Pancreas	333	5831	17.51	314	575
Stomach	149	1630	10.94	291	158

Table 1: Statistics of pathological cases for selected organs at Medical University of Graz from the year 2023.

diagnosis process of a case or later when the WSIs are stored in an archive for further access.

The need for standardized metadata in WSI archives is illustrated by the example of pathology at the Medical University of Graz.

Between 1984 and 2019, pathologists at the Medical University of Graz examined 7,430,001 slides from 1,040,984 cases. That makes around 7 slides per case across different pathological diagnoses.

In the year 2023 there were 54,558 total cases with 397,942 slides at the Medical University of Graz. Some of the cases are listed in Table 1 with additional information of the cases. There were 7,830 colon cases with 31,920 slides. This results in around 4 slides per colon case. Out of the total slides, 876 contained lymph nodes and 2,225 slides were treated with IHC. Numbers for the organs prostate, mamma, lung, liver, kidney, pancreas and stomach are also presented. For pancreas, the average number of slides is almost 18. In some cases there are fewer slides and sometimes there are up to 50 slides per case or even more. This shows the complexity of the pathological work. Information as shown in Table 1 can be extracted from pathology laboratory information and management systems (LIMS).

Pathologists and AI algorithm developers request WSIs from an archive. However, they request single WSIs with specific content e.g, one with cancer tissue on. Instead of desired single WSIs, whole cases are provided, because there is no information on the size of the tumor regions or other metadata in WSI archives available, and in most cases the specific contents of the slides are unknown. Through microscopic inspection, pathologists can identify tissue

types and the presence and extent of tumors on a particular slide. This process is very time-consuming, especially if pathologists are looking for cases with specific WSI content in large WSI archives.

Datasets based on diagnoses, organ types, tissue types or pathological alterations are required for cancer research. This includes clinical studies and AI algorithm development. There are some datasets publicly available for the development of AI algorithms. For example, well-known datasets are TCGA^{1,2}, CAMELYON16^{12,13} or CAMELYON17¹⁴⁻¹⁶. However, the focus is also to use datasets from biobanks^{3,4,17} and similar institutions to train the algorithms with hundreds of thousands WSIs^{18,19}. More institutes are building large cohorts of pathological data for future AI algorithm development. Pathologists select individual WSIs by hand based on diseases, organ types, tissue types or pathological alterations. Each of the slides must be inspected to fulfill the dataset requirements. For each of the slides also metadata information of the patients is collected and added to the dataset. Metadata information can be patient information, such as survival after diagnosis, diagnosis, treatment type or other information. This metadata information must be provided for each slide of the dataset. This process is very time-consuming and standardized metadata can make the WSI selection process much easier.

WSI archives are also used in various fields of biology. There, animal and plant specimens are put on slides, digitized, analyzed and archived. In this field, similar workflows are used to create datasets as in pathology.

Pathologists and researchers can access the data to compare similar cases with each other or train AI algorithms to assist in the diagnosis of cancer^{18,20-22}, segment tissue types²³⁻²⁶ or make survival predictions^{2,27,28}. Currently, the WSIs are managed by big biobanks like Biobank Graz of Medical University of Graz¹⁷. Due to the high numbers of WSIs within and from different cases stored in such biobanks, advanced data access is required. This includes good search capabilities to filter WSIs from specific cases and diagnoses. In most cases, the diagnosis and clinical data are attached as metadata. However, the search process is complex, especially if datasets for training AI algorithms are prepared.

Yet, to extract metadata information from an entire collection of slides, each slide would need to be manually inspected by an expert. An automated retrieval of detailed information from WSIs based on specific source material (organs), tissue types or (pathological) alterations is not yet possible.

This paper suggests adding metadata to a histopathological slide describ-

ing the content of that slide in a low-resolution “tissue map”. This “tissue map” comprises of three levels: level 1 holds information regarding the source material (organ), level 2 holds information regarding the common tissue types, and level 3 holds information regarding (pathological) alterations.

These metadata help to build up WSI catalogs of histopathological slides and enable a FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable) data management²⁹. Such a catalog of histopathological slides is important for medical and biological research as well as for AI-based algorithm development^{21,22,27,28}. Especially in the field of Deep Learning (DL) a part of ML, large amounts of data are required for training neural networks^{18,20,24,26}.

To achieve interoperability of such catalogs and enable the combination of collections of histopathological slides, it is necessary to agree on a common format for these metadata and a standardized description of samples.

This work proposes a metadata model with common syntax and semantics to generate multi-layer tissue maps for WSIs and a profiling mechanism for specific application domains. The model describes each WSI of a collection with a detailed multi-layer tissue map that provides fine-grained information about the WSI content. The tissue map is organized into three layers: source material (organ), common tissue types, and (pathological) alterations. A proof-of-concept implementation for common tissue types and pathological alterations shows the advantages of the metadata model, which contributes to the community standards of BBMRI-ERIC.

This paper is organized as follows: Section 2 lists related work in that research field. Section 3 explains the methodology of the proposed metadata standard with tissue maps and its integration into WSI archives, applications and use cases. Section 4 shows the experimental evaluation, Section 5 shows the discussion and Section 6 concludes the paper and gives an outlook of future work.

2. Related Work

WSIs are increasingly managed by biobanks^{3,4,17} and are accessible either directly or via research infrastructures such as BBMRI-ERIC³⁰. Given the sheer volume of WSIs stored across diverse cases in these biorepositories, advanced data access mechanisms are essential. In particular, robust search capabilities are required to identify WSIs corresponding to specific diagnoses or cases, facilitating the construction of curated datasets for tasks such as

cancer diagnoses^{18,20–22}, tissue segmentation^{23–26} or make survival predictions^{2,27,28}. Due to the manual effort involved in WSI selection, researchers increasingly explore algorithmic solutions to optimize the search process.

In 2019 Hedge et al. introduced a similar image search for histopathology (SMILY)³¹, a deep learning-based framework to search for images in the field of histopathology. Using a selected image patch from a WSI as a query, SMILY identifies similar histological patterns, organ sites, and cancer grades. The underlying neural network was trained on datasets containing general image content (e.g., animals, objects, human faces), eliminating the need for annotated histopathology images. The framework was evaluated on WSIs from prostate, breast, and colon cancers, demonstrating retrieval of relevant histological features including arteries, epithelium, lymphatic vessels, and stroma.

In 2020 Kalra et al. presented Yottixel³² an image search engine for histopathological WSI. Also based on query image inputs, Yottixel enables high-speed search through large-scale WSI archives, returning similar cases and their diagnostic reports. It was evaluated using over 2,000 WSIs from the TCGA dataset for different cancer types and grades.

Building on this, Kalra et al. introduced an advanced AI-based search algorithm²⁰ further scaling the image-query approach. The model was evaluated with almost 11,000 patient WSIs and over 20 million image patches with 32 cancer types and 25 anatomic sites. Results showed strong performance in retrieving visually and clinically similar images based on patch-level similarity.

Chen et al. used Yottixel³² as a foundation and extended it to self-supervised image search for histology (SISH)³³. SISH was trained using slide-level annotations and evaluated across 22,000 cases involving 56 disease types. It demonstrated robustness even in identifying rare cancer subtypes, addressing limitations of data scarcity in conventional models.

While all of these approaches offer powerful patch-level retrieval based on visual similarity, they typically require manual query selection and do not support metadata-based search across entire WSI archives. In contrast, the metadata model with multi-layer tissue maps proposed in this work enables comprehensive search and filtering of WSIs based on structured metadata descriptors.

Metadata extraction from WSIs has also been explored through ML. Weng et al.³⁴ proposed a multimodal multitask learning framework to predict major slide-level metadata, including tissue type, fixation method, sampling

procedure, and staining technique. Their model was trained using information at the patch, slide, and case levels and evaluated on TCGA and internal datasets. However, it lacked granularity regarding tissue subtypes or pathological alterations.

Sirinukunwattana et al.³⁵ developed a method for WSI segmentation into tissue regions using phenotypic profiling. By classifying cells into four types (necrotic debris, malignant epithelial, inflammatory, and spindle-shaped), and constructing cell interaction networks, they labeled regions with six distinct tissue phenotypes. These metadata were used to predict the risk of distant metastasis in colorectal cancer, though not applied to search or catalog enrichment.

Another example is MIKAIA²³, a histopathology-oriented framework designed for clinical research. It supports WSIs from various scanners and utilizes data augmentation to enable generalization. Trained on slides from six different scanners, MIKAIA can automatically annotate nine tissue and alteration classes with high accuracy²⁵, and export results in multiple formats. However, while capable of annotating structures such as fat and muscle tissue, its metadata coverage remains limited relative to the needs of large-scale WSI cataloging.

Collectively, these methods either extract specific metadata or implement image-query search approaches. However, a standardized, comprehensive metadata framework to describe the full content of WSIs across large archives is still lacking. Manual selection of WSIs remains time-consuming, and current methods often do not scale well for large WSI collections. The proposed metadata model, featuring structured multi-layer tissue maps, addresses these limitations. By enabling fine-grained filtering of WSIs based on source (organ), tissue type, or (pathological) alterations, the model facilitates the construction of tailored data cohorts, streamlining AI development in digital pathology.

3. Proposed Metadata Model

The domain field using WSIs is highly diverse, encompassing plant histology, animal research, general histological examinations, and in our case, pathological diagnostics. Therefore, a simple metadata standard is insufficient to cover such areas. Moreover, it is often inadequate to make only a general statement about a slide, as the spatial distribution of different structures contains important information.

Figure 3: Definition of layer profiles based on coding standards and look-up table (LUT) to color definitions. The layer profiles are used to define the tissue map content, which can be visualized with different methods. Examples of tissue map visualizations are segmentation maps or bar charts for each WSI.

To meet these requirements, we have (a) developed a common denominator for all the different areas in the form of a three-layer model and (b) designed the metadata description as a mini-map that encodes spatial information in these three layers.

The three layers, also called "tissue map" defined by the slide metadata model include: (1) the source of the material, (2) the tissue type or other classifications at the microscopic level, and (3) (pathological) alterations or a highlighting layer.

A profile defines the possible values that can be encoded for each layer, as well as their associated semantics through a link to a known ontology. Such encodings in the field of surgical pathology include Uber Anatomy oncol-

ogy (UBERON)^{36,37}, Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine Clinical Terms (SNOMED CT)³⁸, Open Biological Ontologies (OBO)³⁹, BRAunschweig ENzyme DATabase (BRENDA)^{40,41}, International Classification of Diseases of oncology Third Edition (ICD-O-3)^{42,43}, International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problem (ICD-10)⁴⁴ or National Cancer Institute Thesaurus (NCIt)⁴⁵, shown in Figure 3.

If a profile is limited to 256 different values across the three layers, this can be practically encoded in an 8-bit image and stored in common, naturally lossless compressed image formats. The profile maps each entry to a color code via lookup tables (LUT). This allows the visualization of defined source materials, tissue types and (pathological) alterations as segmentation maps, bar charts or with other methods.

In the following, we illustrate how we defined the three layer profiles for "surgical pathology". The defined profiles can be found in the Github repository: <https://github.com/human-centered-ai-lab/WSIDOM>.

3.1. Profile Definition for Tissue Maps

The metadata criteria are selected on oncology and vocabulary to make the standard concrete, simple and practical for comprehensive usage. International coding standards are used. In this work, the three layer profiles (for source, tissue types, pathological alterations) are based on international coding standards describing organs, tissue types and pathological alterations. The first 4 entries of each profile are defined by NULL values similar to the HL7 standard⁴⁶. They are used to describe unknown, not encoded or missing information. The 4 defined NULL values are NI (No Semantics), UNC (Not Encoded), UNK (Unknown) and NV (No proper Value). The rest of the entries are based on the selected coding standards. The source profile is based on ICD-O-3^{42,43} topology, the tissue type profile and the pathological alteration profile use National Cancer Institute Thesaurus (NCIt)⁴⁵ encoding.

A structure is defined to describe each entry of the profile, as shown in an example in Table 2. Each entry starts with an ID element as a unique identifier, followed by a PARENT element. If the entry has no parent, a value of '-1' is assigned, otherwise the ID from the parent entry is used. This allows for the representation of hierarchies inside the profile. Furthermore, international coding standards can be transferred directly into the profiles. The CODE element refers to the used code of a coding standard and defines the name of annotations for the selected tissue map. The element DEF COLOR

Header	Description	Example
ID	Identifier for entry	5
PARENT	Link to parent entry ID	-1
CODE	Coding standard	C50
DEF COLOR	Color of annotation	#000037
COLOR	Color for WSIDOM visualization	#000037
NAME	Name of coding standard entry	Breast
COMMENT	Additional information	Breast source material
ONTOLOGY	URL to coding standard description	https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/ICD-0-3/?p=classes&conceptid=https%3A%2F%2Fdata.jrc.ec.europa.eu%2Fcollection%2FICD03_0%23C50
CONCEPT	URL to coding standard entry ID	https://data.jrc.ec.europa.eu/collection/ICD03_0#C50

Table 2: The breast organ as an example entry of the source material profile.

shows the used color in annotation tools like QuPath^{47–49}, Orbit Image Analysis⁵⁰, or V7 Darwin⁵¹. The COLOR element defines the visualization color for the generated tissue maps. The color values must be encoded in hexadecimal (HEX) format. The NAME element describes the coding and the COMMENT element is used for additional information. ONTOLOGY is an element for a general description or a link to the coding standard description. The CONCEPT element links the coding standard to a concept ID of the used coding standard. This can be a website or a document with a detailed description of the coding. The profiles are stored in csv files. This enables efficient handling of the profiles to generate the tissue maps and is easy to interpret for humans. Interpretability, traceability and thus explainability are therefore not only becoming more important, but are actually mandatory, because upcoming regulations and requirements demand explainability^{52–54}.

Layer 1 defines the source material of the specimen, namely the organ or organ part type on a WSI. In this work, organ types are mapped to codes based on the top-level oncology classes of the ICD-O-3 standard^{42,43}. This standard allows coding for a broader spectrum of specimen material from humans like colon, nose, prostate etc. In total 80 different organ classes are defined at the top-level oncology. Examples of ICD-O-3 codes are C18 for colon, C50 for breast, or C64 for the kidney. The information on the organ types can be extracted from medical reports or clinical data, or it can be predicted by ML algorithms.

Layer 2 defines the tissue types of the specimen. In this work, the layer 2 profile is based on the NCI⁴⁵ encoding for different muscle, nerve,

Figure 4: General process to visualize the tissue maps with WSIDOM as segmentation maps.

connective-tissue types, epithelium and many more. They are structured hierarchically with general tissue types at the higher level followed by a more detailed breakdown. The profile represents selected tissue types and their hierarchies.

Layer 3 defines the (pathological) alterations of the specimen. The used profile is based on NCI⁴⁵ coding standard and defines different pathological alterations like inflammation, necrosis, neoplastic-malignant, neoplastic-benign, neoplastic-metastatic etc. A hierarchical structure is used for general and detailed alterations.

Algorithms can process the tissue maps or they can be visualized in several ways for human inspection with different colors or patterns for each layer. In this work, we use look-up tables (LUT) for the visualization of the tissue maps. The LUT is used to map the entries of each layer to defined color values to create segmentation maps, shown in Figure 3.

3.2. Visualization Framework

This work introduces the framework WSIDOM (Whole-Slide Image Description of Morphology) to visualize the content of WSIs based on the defined profiles. WSIDOM uses the metadata included in the three layer-profiles (source material, tissue type, and (pathological) alterations) to create segmentation maps for human readability. The code is located in the Github repository: <https://github.com/human-centered-ai-lab/WSIDOM>.

An overview of how the framework works is shown in Figure 4. The framework requires a WSI, the defined layer profiles and metadata for each

Figure 5: Visualization of tissue maps as segmentation maps with different colors and alpha values. The original WSI from the TCGA dataset is shown on the left side. The upper row shows the segmentation maps with different visualization colors with an alpha value of 1. The lower row shows the segmentation maps overlaid with the WSI based on the same visualization colors and an alpha value of 0.5.

layer. The profiles of source material, tissue types and pathological alterations provide the look-up table (LUT) to map the entries of each profile to a defined color value. Based on the inputs (i.e., metadata and layer profiles) the WSIDOM framework creates the segmentation maps for source material, tissue types and pathological alterations. The generated segmentation maps have thumbnail sizes with a resolution between 1000×1000 and 2000×2000 pixels. WSIDOM allows to overlay the WSI input with the segmentation maps, by defining a transparency value alpha. The value of alpha can be set between 0 and 1, where 0 is completely transparent and 1 is not transparent.

An example of the results of WSIDOM for visualizing tissue maps is shown in Figure 5. The WSI used for this visualisation example is part of the breast TCGA dataset. In this example, the metadata in the form of annotations were made with QuPath⁴⁷ and exported as geojson files for each layer. The upper row of images in Figure 5 shows the visualized tissue maps with alpha value set to 1 and different LUT for color visualization. The three layers on the right are represented by single-channel colors and visualized as green, blue and red to store the tissue maps in common, naturally lossless compressed image formats. On the left side, the visualization of the tissue maps is done with annotation colors to be human-readable. In the

second row of images in Figure 5, the alpha value is set to 0.5 to overlay the segmentation maps with the input WSI. The different colors show different classes in the corresponding layer. In the source material layer, only the breast organ type is present. In layer 2, Connective-Tissue (CT), Connective-Tissue-Dense (CT-Dense), Connective-Tissue-Loose(CT-Loose), Connective-Tissue-Blood (CT-Blood), Connective-Tissue-Lymphatic (CT-Lymphatic), Connective-Tissue-Fat (Fat), Nerve and Epithelium are present. Layer 3 shows Neoplastic, Neoplastic-Malignant, Inflammation-Chronic and Not Encoded (UNC) regions.

The tissue maps can be visualized in different forms. One way is to use the segmentation maps generated with the WSIDOM framework, as shown in Figure 5. Another method is to calculate the class areas for each layer and present the ratios as bar charts. The area ratios can be normalized differently. One way is to normalize the ratios per resolution of the WSI, other ways are to normalize per specimen area or content area of each layer. Pathologists prefer the normalization per specimen area, so that they can directly see the size of tumor regions. Figure 6 illustrates this visualization method on an example WSI from the TCGA breast dataset. In the example shown in Figure 6, the classes are normalized per sub-regions for each layer. In this example, the source material (organ) is 100% C50 (breast). This layer can be used to split slides with multiple samples to separate slides, similar to Plass et al.⁵⁵. Layer 2 contains several tissue types. The most common tissue type in the example WSI is Connective-Tissue, which is further divided into Connective-Tissue-Fat (56.93%), Connective-Tissue-Dense (20.43%), Connective-Tissue-Loose (5.93%), Connective-Tissue-Blood (2.7%) and Connective-Tissue-Lymphatic (0.98%). Also, Epithelium with 8.16% and Nerve tissue with 0.28% are present. The main part in Layer 3 is Neoplastic-Malignant with more than 60%, followed by Not Encoded with almost 30%. Also, Neoplastic (5.91%) and Inflammation-Chronic (3.31%) alterations are present.

Area ratios as meta-information of tissue maps advance the search and filter capabilities of WSI archives. The visualization of the area ratios can be extended to multiple slides as shown in Figure 7. Such a visualization in WSI archives allows to inspect multiple slides at the same time and extract relevant information from WSIs very quickly. Each WSI is represented with three bars. The first bar shows layer 1, the source material. One slide can contain several source materials. Typically, this occurs with biopsies of closely situated organs such as the colon and liver. The second and third

Figure 6: Visualization of tissue composition from the example WSI. For better visibility, the areas are normalized per content of each tissue map layer.

Figure 7: Example of a possible visualization of WSI content in catalogs or WSI archives. Each WSI composition is represented with the three layers source material, tissue type and pathological alteration. The visualization color is defined by a LUT in the layer profiles.

bars show the area ratios of layer 2 (tissue types) and layer 3 (pathological alterations) respectively. Due to this attention-based approach, a pathologist can make faster decisions to select relevant WSIs for research purposes even without inspecting the WSI. Also, the search parameters of the WSI archive can be adjusted quickly by using information from this visualization. Furthermore, such detailed information of the WSI content simplifies the work in pathological laboratories, and prospective pathologists can be trained more efficiently by targeted selection of WSIs with specific content.

3.3. Dataset

A catalog was built with WSIs of 99 slides from TCGA dataset¹ across different organs like uterine, colon, lung, kidney, skin and more. The TCGA dataset contains regions of different tissue types and pathological alterations.

All slides were loaded into V7 Darwin⁵¹ and only some areas of the WSIs were annotated based on the defined classes from the layer profiles of the tissue maps. Slides contain one or multiple annotation classes from tissue types and pathological alterations. Pathologists reviewed the annotations. The annotations of the TCGA slides are provided in the Github repository.

3.4. Tissue Classifier

Experiments are done with the integration of the proposed standard into WSI catalogs and for training AI algorithms. The overall design of the experiment was to obtain preliminary results by applying binary classifiers for defined tissue types and pathological alterations. Binary classifiers were used to estimate and limit the difficulty of the task.

Binary classifiers were used for 5 different tissue type classes, Connective-Tissue-Fat, Connective-Tissue, Muscle, Epithelium and Nerve and 6 pathological alterations Neoplastic, Neoplastic-Metastatic, Neoplastic-Malignant, Neoplastic-Benign, Necrosis, and Inflammation-Chronic, across different organs. Because of the partly annotated areas of the WSIs and the resulting unbalanced data, the pathological alterations were combined into one class and trained with a binary classifier.

Patches of size 512×512 pixels are extracted from the annotated areas of the WSIs. Patches are shifted with a stride of 128 pixels in x and y directions so that they overlap during the tiling process. The extracted patches are used for the training of the binary classifiers. Some patches have overlapping annotations. Hence, there are two approaches to managing overlapping annotations. First, the patch belongs to the tissue type if the tissue type is in the list of covered tissue types. The other method would only consider the patch belonging to a tissue type if the tissue type has the highest occurrence (strict labeling). In this work, strict labeling is used.

As a base model, VGG16⁵⁶ was used as a feature extractor with pre-trained weights on ImageNet⁵⁷. The model was modified to handle an input size of 512×512 pixels and fine-tuned for the pathology tasks. For a binary classification, a global max pooling layer and a classifier head consisting of a dropout layer were added followed by a fully connected layer. Each model was trained with the same settings: batch size of 32, learning rate of 5e-05, L2 regularization of 5e-05 and trained for a maximum of 50 epochs.

The binary classifiers are trained with 72 WSIs of the TCGA dataset and evaluated on 27 TCGA test slides. In total 242,716 patches are extracted from the annotated regions and used for training. Each classifier is evaluated

Classifier	Train # of patches	Test # of patches
Tissue Types		
Connective-Tissue-Fat	31,706	16,984
Connective-Tissue	17,432	7,525
Muscle	9,883	11,654
Epithelium	4,210	2,215
Nerve	370	620
Pathological Alterations		
Neoplastic-Malignant	144,715	99,689
Neoplastic-Metastatic	6,342	14,555
Neoplastic-Benign	1,031	834
Necrosis	21,748	14,139
Inflammation-Chronic	5,288	4,163
Pathological Alterations (total)	179,124	133,380
Total	242,716	172,378

Table 3: Number of patches extracted from the annotated regions for training and testing the binary classifiers. Binary classifiers are trained for each tissue type and one binary classifier is trained for all pathological alterations.

on 27 partly annotated test WSIs. For the evaluation 172,378 patches are extracted from the annotated areas of the test slides and classified. The results are compared with the annotation classes and the average accuracy over the test WSIs for each classifier is calculated. The distribution of the extracted patches for training and testing is shown in Table 3. The patches are unbalanced, which can lead to biased multi-class classifiers. Therefore, a metadata description of the WSI content is essential to build balanced datasets for digital pathology.

4. Experimental Evaluation of the Metadata Model

The trained and validated classifiers are used to segment the entire WSIs of the test set. Each WSI is divided into patches. Each patch is classified and overlapping patches are averaged to generate a prediction segmentation map for each binary classifier. The segmentation maps of each classifier are combined to form the tissue maps of tissue type and pathological alterations. The tissue maps are combined with certain rules: Overlapping regions between neighboring patches are averaged, which can result in border artifacts.

Task	Accuracy
Connective-Tissue-Fat	0.9476
Connective-Tissue	0.8972
Muscle	0.9209
Epithelium	0.9365
Nerve	0.9440
Pathological Alterations	0.9359

Table 4: Averaged accuracy of each binary classifier.

If more classifiers give a stronger prediction (above 50%), the area is marked as uncertain; if all classifier predictions are below 50%, the area is left unclassified otherwise, strict labeling is used. For pathological alterations, a segmentation map is created, where overlapping classified patches can result in different values (lower and above 50%). Such areas are labeled as uncertain. If overlapping patches are classified with stronger prediction (above 50%), the areas are labeled as pathological alterations. If the predictions are lower than 50% the area is labeled as unclassified.

The evaluation of the classifiers is done with patches only from the partly annotated regions of the TCGA test slides. Patches are extracted from the annotated areas and each binary classifier is evaluated. Some class annotations are not present in most of the slides. E.g. Nerve tissue is only annotated in a few of the 27 TCGA test slides. Therefore, only the average accuracy over all test data for each binary classifier is presented in Table. 4. There are 5 binary classifiers for tissue types and one combined binary classifier for pathological alterations. The overall accuracy of each binary classifier is very high. The entire WSIs were not evaluated and border cases might be missed due to the evaluation with only annotated areas.

4.1. Visualization of Classifier Results

Each classifier creates a prediction segmentation map for each tissue type and pathological alteration. The results are combined based on the classified patches with the defined classes inside the tissue maps. Each tissue map is independent of each other and separately analyzed. This results for tissue types in areas of uncertainty, marked as gray or unclassified (light gray). In the case of tissue type, light blue shows Connective-Tissue-Fat, blue shows Connective-Tissue, green highlights Epithelium, brown shows Muscle and yellow marks Nerve tissue, as shown in Figure 8. Black shows the background.

Figure 8: Example segmentation maps for tissue type classifiers and the combined segmentation map with background (black), unclassified (light gray), uncertain (gray) and tissue regions with Epithelium (green), Nerve (yellow), Connective-Tissue-Fat (light blue), Connective-Tissue (blue) and Muscle (brown).

The same approach is used for the pathological alterations, where pathological alterations are red, uncertain regions are gray, due to overlapping patches with different classifications, unclassified areas are light gray and the background is black. Results for both layers (left tissue types and right pathological alterations) are shown in Figure 9. The results are evaluated with pathologists. The metadata for layer 1 (source) is extracted from the WSI description, and no classifier is required.

It can be seen, that the binary classifiers struggle with exact border delineation between different tissue types and pathological alterations. This is due to the patch-based approach for classification, strict labeling and the combination of each single prediction segmentation map to one combined segmentation map.

The combined segmentation maps for tissue types and pathological alterations are analyzed and the area ratios of the different classified areas are calculated. Figure 10 shows the composition of the specimen with the predicted tissue types on examples of the test slides. The area ratios are normalized per specimen area (background excluded). This normalization is preferred by pathologists. Meta information is used to define the organ type.

Figure 9: Tissue maps of layers tissue type and pathological alteration visualized as segmentation maps for different WSIs of the test dataset. Tissue types of WSIs are shown on the left with background (black), unclassified (light gray), uncertain (gray), Epithelium (green), Nerve (yellow), Connective-Tissue-Fat (light blue), Connective-Tissue (blue) and Muscle (brown). The pathological alterations for the same WSIs are shown on the right with background (black), unclassified (light gray), uncertain (gray) and pathological alterations with Neoplastic, Neoplastic-Metastatic, Neoplastic-Malignant, Neoplastic-Benign, Necrosis, and Inflammation-chronic (red). Each layer is independent of each other.

In all 4 example WSIs, high densities of Connective-Tissue can be observed. The density of other tissue types varies. Each of the slides has a high density of pathological alterations.

A full overview of the composition of the test dataset (WSI catalog) is shown in Figure 11. The majority of the test slides contain a high density

Figure 10: Composition analysis of the layers source (organ), tissue types and pathological alterations for example WSIs of the test dataset. The first bar shows the organ source material, the second shows the composition of the tissue type layer and the third bar shows the composition of the pathological alteration layer for different WSIs.

Figure 11: Composition analysis of the layers source (organ), tissue types and pathological alterations for TCGA test slides. The composition of each WSI is represented with area ratios of the specimen with bars for source material, tissue type and pathological alterations.

of Connective-Tissue with up to 77%. There are also slides with a high density of Muscle tissue and Epithelium. Some regions are unclassified and uncertain due to the small number of defined tissue classes. Nerve tissue is only present in small proportions in some of the slides. Most of the slides have a high concentration of pathological alterations around 50% and above. Such analysis allows detailed metadata description of the composition of the slides and entire WSI cohorts. Databases can be updated with these metadata-

based search parameters to filter WSIs based on specific composition criteria. This makes the selection of slides and the creation of specific datasets for research easier.

5. Discussion

This paper introduces a cross-catalog metadata standard with multi-layer tissue maps to describe the morphology of WSIs for large-scale WSI archives. It is based on a three-layer model with source, tissue type and pathological alterations. Each layer forms a tissue map based on a defined profile with common syntax and notations to fulfill the requirements of surgical pathology or biology use cases.

Currently, vision transformer⁵⁸ based on self-supervised learning⁵⁹ or multiple instance learning²¹ are popular for digital pathology: Transformer-based models^{28,60,61} are used to predict survival rates^{27,28,60}, to classify/detect cancer types^{60,62,63}, and also for tissue segmentation^{26,64}.

But ML models do not yet process entire WSIs at once during training due to the WSI's big resolution of up to $150,000 \times 150,000$ pixels. Therefore, WSIs are divided into small patches and at each training iteration a subset of these patches is sampled²⁸. Researchers are trying to increase the size of the patches^{60,61} across different pyramid levels. The size of a patch can be increased up to $32,768 \times 32,768$ pixels⁶³ by applying dilated attention⁶⁵ and with an up-scale framework TORCHSCALE⁶⁶. Larger patch sizes require more advanced hardware platforms, which are often not available.

However, random sampling can be suboptimal. The probability of sampling a random patch in an image with a specific pathological alteration is determined by the specific pathological alteration and the full image area. The same applies to tissue types and organ types. Random sampling can lead to underrepresented classes and imbalanced training data and consequently to biased models. Therefore, this patch extraction benefits from the 8-bit encoding representing the defined classes of the tissue maps: With a more advanced WSI selection process, WSIs can be selected based on fine-grained information on the composition of the specimen. This can help to counteract data imbalance in the training data for ML models as it allows uniform sampling of training data across classes.

Another use of the tissue maps for ML in digital pathology involves utilizing the class assignments from the tissue maps as feature representation for ML, as shown in Figure 12(a). The class assignments from the tissue

Figure 12: Examples of possible WSI representations. (a) Feature representation with the tissue maps and their associated color channels of an RGB image. (b) Graph-based WSI representation by using the tissue maps.

maps are concatenated with the raw image data of the WSI. Each of the layers corresponds to a dimension in this novel feature space. By providing this contextual information together with raw pixel values, ML models get a much deeper understanding of the WSI content. Tissue maps enable a more effective and efficient learning of the models.

This paper introduces the first experiments with binary classifiers for different tissue types and pathological alterations to automate the process of tissue map generation from WSIs and the metadata analysis about the content of WSIs across catalogs. It shows on the example of a TCGA dataset the composition of each WSI in the test set. It demonstrates the advantages of the defined layer profiles and the generated metadata of each tissue map for WSI search and dataset creation. This paper shows the representation of WSIs as multi-layer tissue maps as a metadata standard and possibilities for applications. WSIs can be processed with foundation models to classify^{18,35,67}, segment^{23,67} or annotate²⁵ histological images or predict pathological workflow parameters³⁴.

However, the metadata model approach presented in this paper includes the WSI metadata directly into WSI archives as multi-layer tissue maps, where this information can be used by filter operations in biobank management tools such as OpenSpecimen⁶⁸. This gives a big advantage for the selection of WSI for future research projects.

The definition of the tissue maps based on source, tissue types and patho-

logical alterations as three layers allows a representation as a single RGB color image, which is suitable as input features for the development of ML algorithms in digital pathology^{20,22}. Additionally, the tissue maps help to counteract unbalanced training data and provide more efficient and effective training of ML models.

In recent years, researchers also try to extract spatial information with graph transformers from different magnification levels of WSIs and learn the relationships of these levels to build classifiers or detectors for different pathological tasks⁶⁹⁻⁷². Each of these works takes patches from different magnification levels of the WSI and builds frameworks to construct graphs based on the information of these patches to improve different classification tasks.

With tissue maps a spatial relationship between the 3 layers (source material, tissue types, pathological alterations) is established by forming a graph-based representation with pathological entities of the WSI^{69,71}. In this graph-based representation, the nodes of the graph represent the classes of segmented areas of the different layers and the weights represent the distance of the spatial relationship between the nodes. Such a graph-based representation of a WSI is shown schematically in Figure 12(b). By providing tissue maps with the three layers source material, tissue types and (pathological) alterations, ML models can be trained with graph-based methods⁶⁹⁻⁷². The models can learn from the spatial relationships between each of these layers to find dependencies related to cancer research.

The three layers of the tissue map enable the extraction of additional information from WSIs, such as WSI content-specific area ratios for present source material types (organs), tissue types or (pathological) alterations. WSI archives include the WSI-specific information as metadata.

A test dataset is used to show the integration of the proposed metadata standard into WSI archives, which allows to build large-scale WSI archives with specific search capabilities from organs/organ types, tissue types, pathological alterations to specimen composition of WSIs across catalogs. WSI archives include the WSI-specific information as metadata. Thus, by providing more information about the WSI content, the search functionality of the WSI archives can be significantly increased by filtering the WSIs based on the specific parameters required from pathologists or researchers. Such particular parameters can be the source material, tissue types or (pathological) alterations represented by the three layers of the tissue map. By calculating the area for each defined entry in each layer, desired WSIs can be

extracted from the WSI archive to build WSI catalogs based on these search parameters. The search capability will be included in biobank management systems to enable new possibilities for faster and more precise WSI selections for different research fields. Specific and balanced WSI catalogs can be built for medical studies or to improve AI algorithm training for digital pathology. Based on these search capabilities, datasets for digital pathology or similar fields can be created and selected from archives more efficiently and effectively and further used for the development of AI algorithms and the creation of validation datasets^{73,74}. This is a different approach compared to the image query-based approaches described by Hedge et al.³¹, Kalra et al.^{20,32} and Chen et al.³³, where query images are used to find images with similar morphological structures. These structures can be histopathological features, cancer grading or cancer subtyping.

Incorporating prior knowledge of the content within a WSI holds substantial potential to enhance the performance of AI algorithms during both the training and inference phases. Standardized interfaces foster seamless integration, comparability, and collaboration across diverse platforms and stakeholders. In this context, the Ecosystem for Pathology Diagnostics with AI Assistance (EMPAIA)^{73,74} has been pivotal in developing APIs that support such connectivity and interoperability. EMPAIA serves as a comprehensive ecosystem for digital pathology, promoting collaboration among pathologists, industry leaders, and computer scientists. It provides a robust framework for evaluating various AI algorithms, thereby streamlining the adoption and assessment of new technological innovations in the field.

EMPAIA's suite of ML algorithms supports pathological diagnostics by offering a structured approach to testing and incorporating diverse analytical tools. The planned integration of the multi-layer tissue maps within EMPAIA's platform represents a significant advancement, enabling a more refined evaluation of digital pathology solutions. Embedding the proposed metadata standard through a standardized interface will enhance the process of selecting WSIs based on tissue maps and defined criteria, making the training and assessment of algorithms more efficient. Through this integration, EMPAIA will strengthen its capability to support precise and efficient algorithm evaluation and deployment in digital pathology.

6. Conclusion

This paper introduces a metadata model framework to generate 2D index maps, also called tissue map, to profile the content of WSIs. The tissue map is organized into three layers with source material (organ), common tissue types and (pathological) alterations providing fine-grained information about the content of the WSI. Segments of the WSI are assigned to predefined classes within these layers. This layered approach enhances WSI collections by supporting more effective and efficient content-based search. An experimental evaluation in the pathology domain demonstrates the interoperability of the proposed metadata model by employing standardized syntax and semantics across different catalogs. A test catalog based on TCGA WSIs illustrates the metadata model’s utility and its integration into a WSI archive with a focus on improved search functionality.

An open-source framework, WSIDOM, is developed to support visualization and conversion of annotations from commonly used tools into tissue maps. WSIDOM is user-friendly, adaptable to different tissue map profiles, and designed to meet the needs of diverse research applications. The framework is available at: <https://github.com/human-centered-ai-lab/WSIDOM>.

Future work will focus on leveraging a larger and more balanced set of annotations to train a multi-class tissue segmentation model at the patch level. This will further automate metadata extraction based on predefined tissue map profiles. Additionally, extending various WSI catalogs with this metadata model will enable advanced, content-aware search capabilities across WSI repositories.

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8. Contributors

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10. Declaration of interests

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

11. Data Sharing Statement

We used the public datasets from The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA) (<https://www.cancer.gov/ccg/research/genome-sequencing/tcga>).

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